

Book Review

Žižek, Slavoj.

Christian Atheism: How to Be a Real Materialist.

London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2024. Pp. 312. Pb. £14.99.

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Around Chicagoland, I always darted towards the philosophy section of these bookshops. There I discovered Žižek. I devoured one book after another. I bought all his expensive books, draining all my savings, as a good capitalist consumer intent on satiating my ravenous appetite to read all of his works.

The Slovenian Žižek is the rock star in philosophy today, just like Sartre and de Beauvoir in the peak of their careers. The former appeals to Anglophones, while the latter appeal to Francophones. Foucault and Marcuse were other rock stars of philosophy during their prime, appealing to both sides of the Atlantic pond. Žižek is a prolific writer. His reputation precedes him. This book is situated in the realm of philosophy and intersects with theology.

Žižek claims to be a proponent of communism, Hegel, Lacan and Lenin, all of which are crucial to understand his book. In summary, the book starts with an introduction. It has six chapters and a conclusion. Žižek presented the argument according to which, for atheism to be true, it has to be indirectly, not directly, rejecting the notion of a divinity. The author argued that religion will meet its own demise as a result of its innate tensions. This book has the obligatory so-called Lacanian psychoanalysis of Buddhism. Next, the author discussed his notions of 'superposition' and 'athings'. Žižek analysed the sacred, obscene and undead and argued that politics is immanent. He concluded by stating that psychoanalysis is needed.

The cardinal treatise of this book was that authentic atheism is not direct. It requires a critical view of not only ideas of religion but also of materialist secularist ideas. Žižek employed both psychoanalytic and philosophical tools to investigate the way in which atheistic views intertwine with theology. Here,

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he revealed the way in which indirectly approaching atheism by way of the

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auto-exhaustion of religion and the resort to psychoanalysis generates a deeper understanding of materialist viewpoint. There are a few themes covered in this book. They include Christian, atheist, materialist views; psychoanalytic understanding; the relationship between political and religious perspectives and subjectivity.

To those who want to explore the relationship among religious and philosophical ideas, they are most welcome to read this book. The author could provoke and stimulate your mental appetite, as he provides his signature connection between Lacan and Hegel. Note that Žižek's style is dense and you have swim through the mud to find some enlightenment.

His literary style is flawed for several reasons. One, he tends to write in a circuitous manner with sentences as long as ten lines. He goes on and on tangentially. Second, the author is somewhat old fashioned in his writing style, as he tries to impress his readers with unnecessary Latin words, such as 'Neque Homo Neque Deus Neque Natura', which is the title of chapter 5. He could have just written 'Neither Man, Nor God, Nor Nature' and not be pretentious. Perhaps, as in the old school, the author thought that by being obscure and unreadable, his readers would think he is brilliant. On the contrary, by Latinising, he turns off the regular reader who is versed in neither philosophy or Latin. Times have changed. This practice is a reflection of the old but erroneous belief according to which if no one understands what you say, people believe you are intelligent. Žižek is famously not known as a good writer with crystal clear arguments. Yet, his fanatic audience adores his flair for the dramatic with a touch of his own brand of humour. Some authors remind me of the need to write simply and directly. They include novelist Ernest Hemingway, Cornell University English professor William Strunk Jr., and British author Sir Ernest Gowers, both of the latter of whom taught us to use plain words and write short, direct sentences. Additionally, novelist George Orwell and quantum physicist Richard Feynman advocated writing clearly and rejected jargon, as intricate language clouds the main arguments. In this sense, if judging him only by his writing style, Žižek is a dismal failure in writing his philosophical treatise.

In terms of evidence and quality of argument, Žižek's ideas are provocative yet too impenetrable for the regular reader to follow. His approach is quite different for most academics and researchers in the fields of religion and philosophy. On a positive note, Žižek was able to enter into dialogue with both atheism and materialism simultaneously, which proposes a novel outlook. He provided a fresh view of the tension between philosophical and religious ideas. On a negative note, he beats around the bush and his writing is full of unnecessary jargons. He overgeneralises complex ideas in theology. Secularists will have difficulty taking in the ideas laid down in this book, as will theologians.

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In comparative context, one contribution of Žižek is his engagement with Christian thought. This strength must be recognised. However, his weakness was his lack of deep philosophical engagement with non-Christian religions, unlike other philosophers. He was rambling exotic Buddhist vocabulary and throwing Althusser and Marx here and there to sound deep. Here, he bashed Buddhism. In this book, he was hiding under the skirt of Lacanianism. Many other thinkers who came way before Žižek have been more erudite than him in their philosophical treatment of Buddhism, Hinduism and Taoism, such as H. Bergson, Deleuze, R. W. Emerson, R. Guénon, Hegel himself, Heidegger, A. Huxley, Jung, Nietzsche, E. Said, Sartre and Schopenhauer. In this way, Žižek's book is indeed one step forward, but it is also two steps backward. This is my personal reflection. This book comes at an opportune time, as religion is on the decline, at least in the global North. However, this book has more bells and whistles than substance, especially as there are countless biases and limitations in this work. First, the author's dependence on Lacanian psychoanalytic understanding gives him a tunnel view of Christianity and atheism. Second, just like a sophomoric essay, he provides one answer to a complex question. His Lacanianism alienates the uninitiated readers. Third, he delves deeply into the abstract and falls short on providing solid social scientific evidence based on actual cases to buttress his ideational arguments. Fourth, while Hegelianism and Lacanianism appear prominently in this book, I see no trace of his self-proclaimed Marxist communism and Leninism in this work.

I recommend Žižek to explore philosophical speculations beyond his lazy dependence on Lacanian psychoanalysis. However, he is already too fixed in his old ways. I believe it is perhaps already too late for him to study other strands in philosophy. Alas, I would be foolish to ask him to be a better writer who writes clearly, as he is already a rock star and he has no need to improve his writing. In conclusion, despite its shortcomings, this book has some value. Readers are enjoined to practice self-criticism. Oftentimes, there are two sides: atheism or Christianity. The author enjoins us not to ignore the tension between the two, but to engage in an intellectual struggle between secularism and religion. His solution, though, was to enter into Lacanian psychoanalytic mode to understanding the linkage between materialism and atheism. By doing so, his analysis at the end of the day was subjective. His strength is also his weakness. With all its strengths and weaknesses, students of divinity, philosophy, psychology, religion and theology would still benefit from reading this book.

Payap University, Chiang Mai

Rey Ty